

Effect of Gender-Based School Categories on Biology Academic Performance

Chemutai, I. S.¹ and Samikwo, D.¹

¹University of Eldoret

*Corresponding author's Email: dsamikwo@uoeld.ac.ke

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ABSTRACT

Background: In the last few years, there has been a concerning decline in the performance of students in biology, leading to concerns about their ability to access courses that require satisfactory grades in the subject. Therefore, the current study sought to find out the students' attitudes towards biology practical work per school category and their academic performance in biology. A total of 23 biology teachers were purposively sampled, and 245 students were randomly selected in the schools. The data were collected using mixed methods approach integrating both qualitative and quantitative data collection. The data collection tools were questionnaires, interviews, and administering a biology practical test to students to determine their performance.

Findings: In terms of the relationship between gender and attitudes towards biology practical work, female students demonstrated a higher inclination towards expressing positive attitudes compared to male students. Notably, school categories based on gender, ownership, and administrative/academic characteristics demonstrated distinct attitudes and performance patterns. Practical test performance varied significantly across the school categories based on administrative/academic characteristics, with Extra-county schools showing the highest mean performance (9.23 ± 1.2), followed by County schools (6.88 ± 0.9), and Sub-county schools with the lowest mean performance (4.32 ± 0.6). These findings emphasize the need for targeted strategies to address attitudes and foster a conducive learning environment, ultimately improving overall academic performance in biology.

Conclusion and recommendations: These findings emphasize the need for targeted strategies to address attitudes and foster a conducive learning environment, ultimately improving overall academic performance in biology. Policymakers and educators can utilize these insights to implement effective interventions and support students in their biology education journey, paving the way for better educational outcomes.

Keywords: Attitude, Performance, School Category

1. INTRODUCTION

The impact of students' attitudes toward science is crucial, considering the increasing integration of technology into all sectors of the economy. Research studies in the United States have focused on strategies to enhance the quantity and quality of science education (Shapka & Keating, 2003). Science education's significance in the development of any nation is evident through the success of science and technology in developed countries. This study specifically centred on biology, a subject that consistently demonstrates poor performance globally, despite its importance for numerous careers in fields like Medicine, Zoology, Botany, and many more. The issue of poor performance in Biology is not limited to a specific region but is a global concern, as evidenced by research from the United States, Canada, Portugal, Jamaica, and various countries in Africa (Yadav & Mishra, 2013). Additionally, the performance of Biology among secondary school students in East Africa, Africa, and globally has been on the decline (Amedu, 2015). The consistently poor performance has raised significant concerns among educators and stakeholders in the global education sector.

In Kenya, the performance of students in Biology, as measured by the KCSE mean scores, has been consistently low across the country (Millar, 2004). This has led to public outcry and debates over the massive failure, particularly in science subjects like biology (Shapka & Keating, 2003). One possible cause of this poor performance is attributed to the change in the question format, which has shifted from focusing on students' ability to an analytical approach. However, the preparation among candidates has not adapted to this change, as students are expected to apply their acquired knowledge rather than merely memorize information. Feedback from teachers suggests a deliberate shift that may undermine the country's education system through unfair grading of candidates (Osborne, 2003).

The overall low performance in science, and particularly in biology, among the four finalists (KCSE), continues to be a major source of concern for stakeholders, especially in an era of urbanization and globalization, where modern biology faces a variety of socioeconomic and environmental challenges. The current study aims to bridge this gap by investigating students' attitudes towards biology practical work per school category and their academic performance in biology in Turbo Sub-County, Kenya.

1.1 Problem Statement

In the last half a decade, the Kenya National Examination for Secondary Education (KCSE) results have consistently revealed poor performance in biology (KNEC, 2018-2022). The poor performance can be attributed to a number of factors, including ineffective science teachers, overcrowded classrooms, a lack of science equipment, and negative student attitudes towards biology and practical science (Ngakhala, 2021). Practical biology work is necessary for gaining practical experience and developing scientific skills. A study that examines how attitudes change throughout compulsory secondary science education has yet to be conducted. While research suggests that teachers believe practical work has a positive impact on students' attitudes (Holstermann *et al.*, 2009), students have rarely been asked to express their thoughts

on practical work in isolation from science lessons in general. As a result, the current study sought to fill a research gap (by encouraging students to express their opinions) by investigating the relationship between school category and academic performance in Turbo Sub-County, Kenya.

1.2 Objectives

The objective of the study was to investigate students' attitudes towards biology practical work per school category and their academic performance in biology.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The major emphasis on this section is to review the previous studies on school category and biology performance, particularly in the context of practical work.

2.1 The impact of school category on academic performance in biology

Secondary school students' attitudes towards biology performance are critical to their academic achievements and future career paths. Multiple factors, including the type of school they attend, can influence their attitudes. Many educational systems divide schools into tiers based on their location, resources, and academic standards. The purpose of this literature review is to investigate the effects of school categories, specifically extra-county, county, and sub-county schools, on attitudes towards performance in biology among secondary school students. Extra-county schools are distinguished by higher academic standards, cutting-edge infrastructure, well-equipped laboratories, and qualified teachers. Several studies have looked into the effects of extra-county schools on students' attitudes towards biology performance. According to research, students who attend extra-county schools have more positive attitudes towards biology than their counterparts in other school categories. Extra-county schools provide a stimulating learning environment by providing state-of-the-art laboratory facilities, resources, and experienced biology teachers. This environment encourages students' curiosity, enthusiasm, and motivation, resulting in more positive attitudes towards the subject. According to DFID (2007), three critical components of teaching and learning resources (TLR) are physical facilities, human resources, and material resources.

TLR adequacy refers to the sufficiency of material resources, physical facilities, and human resources in terms of both quality and quantity. The accessibility and adequacy of instructional materials, particularly textbooks, have a significant impact on students' performance in a given subject (Padmanabham, 2001). Inadequate TLR can cause instructors to treat science subjects like biology as abstract and uninteresting, which has a negative impact on student engagement. Proper personnel, physical facilities, and instructional materials planning and allocation are critical to supporting educational efforts. TLR scarcity, such as textbooks, libraries, computer laboratories, and science laboratories, can impede the education system's ability to respond effectively to emerging demands (Coombs, 1970). Better learning materials, physical facilities, and human resources are required to improve the quality and efficiency of education, particularly in county and sub-county schools where resource constraints are more prevalent.

Recent research has looked into the sufficiency and distribution of TLR, as well as their effects on students' attitudes and performance in exams like the KCSE.

These studies have revealed the scarcity of TLR in schools, particularly in sub-county schools, posing a challenge to educators and students' attitudes towards subjects. Momoh (2010) discovered that TLR has a significant impact on students' performance and attitude in examinations in her study on the impact of instructional resources on education. TLR was made available due to students' positive attitudes and concrete understanding of science concepts, which discouraged rote learning. TLR inadequacy jeopardizes the educational process, resulting in negative attitudes and lower performance among students. Adeogum (2001) discovered a strong positive relationship between academic performance and teaching resources. When compared to schools with insufficient TLR, schools with more resources tend to perform better. Textbooks, charts, audio-visual materials, and electronic resources are examples of material resources in biology. Similar research by Babayomi (1999) and Mwiria (1985) supports the idea that the quality and quantity of TLR have a significant influence on students' attitudes and performance.

Schools that have adequate facilities, such as textbooks, outperform their less well-equipped counterparts in examinations. Poor academic performance and negative attitudes are linked to inadequate equipment and learning materials. The adequacy of teaching and learning resources determines whether an education system succeeds or fails. The students-to-teacher ratio (STR), which indicates the number of students assigned to each teacher, is one method of determining teacher adequacy. STR can assist in determining whether available resources are being underutilized or overutilized (Afolabi, 2005). Human resources include both teachers and non-teaching personnel. A sufficient number of human resources, particularly teachers, should be employed to ensure successful performance in biology practical, particularly in sub-county schools.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

The study used a descriptive cross-sectional research design to establish the relationship between gender-based categorization of schools and performance in biology practical work.

3.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in Turbo Sub-County, situated between longitudes 34⁰50' east and 35⁰37' west. This sub-county comprises four educational zones: Kapyemit, Sugoi, Kiplombe, and Turbo. It shares its borders with Lugari Constituency to the West, Nandi County to the South, and Kakamega County to the Western (refer to Appendix VI). The area's elevation stands at approximately 1500 meters above sea level, covering a total land area of 324 km². Turbo Sub-County experiences high population density attributed to rapid urbanization (GOK, 2003). The choice of Turbo Sub-County as the study area was influenced by its historical underperformance in the Biology KCSE examination.

3.3 Target Population

A target population of 4442 respondents from three school categories present within Turbo Sub-County, including Extra-County (4), County (5), and Sub-county (37) schools, was selected. These schools were further classified as single-sex or mixed-gender schools, with the distribution as follows: Girls (4), Boys (3), and Mixed (39).

3.4 Sampling Techniques

The researcher used probability sampling methods. The probability techniques used in this study were stratified and simple random sampling. Stratified random sampling was used to select the schools because they are heterogeneous (Kothari, 2009). The strata consisted of schools based on the school category. From the sampled schools, purposive sampling was then used to select teachers teaching biology and students taking biology in form four.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The study therefore computed the student sample size using the average figure of 20 percent following Fisher's formula (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2009);

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2} \cdot \frac{a}{22p} (1-p)}{d^2}$$

$Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ = standard normal variation (at 5% type 1 error ($p < 0.05$), which is 1.96.

p = expected proportion in population based on survey/ pilot studies. d = absolute error or precision decided by the researcher. Therefore, the student sample size was computed as:

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{1.962 \times 0.20(1-0.20)}{0.05^2} = 245.3624 = 245$$

Hence the total sample size of the learners was 245 (125 females, 120 males). On this basis the sample size comprised of 60 males, 61 females, and 119 respondents from mixed school.

Table 1: Sample distribution

Strata (school category)	Target population	Sample size
Male	1056	60
Female	1204	61
Mixed	2060	119
Total	4320	282

3.7 Research Instruments

Primary data was used in the investigation. A questionnaire with both structured and unstructured questions was considered to be the most preferred technique of data collection as it allows one to reach a large group of the population, and it is also economical.

3.8 Data collection procedure

The collection of data was done by one-on-one interviews, observation method, or the drop-and-pick method. The research collected both quantitative and qualitative data as the recommended approach in social science research, which is used to produce meaningful data,

analysis, design, evaluation, and results. The respondents were also considered to be more fruitful in areas where the research may encounter controversies while in the field.

3.10 Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (measures of central tendency and measures of variations) and inferential analysis to achieve the objectives of the study. The process of data analysis involved several stages: the completed questionnaires were edited for completeness and consistency, checked for errors and omissions. Both qualitative and quantitative data was generated from the study. The data was then analyzed using SPSS Version 26 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

The interviewer adhered to these principles by obtaining the necessary permissions from the relevant department before commencing data collection activities. During the research period, research ethical guidelines were put into place to enable the researcher to go ahead and collect data: The dignity and well-being of the respondents have to be protected at all times.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The schools sampled were categorized as males' schools, females' schools, and mixed. The boys and female schools were categorized as single sex schools. From the findings, majority (84.8%) of the respondents were in mixed schools, while 15.2% were in single sex schools.

Table 2: School Category based on gender

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male schools	3	6.5
Female schools	4	8.7
Mixed Schools	39	84.8
Total	46	100

The students were presented with questionnaires with different attitudes towards biology practical and were required to indicate whether they agree or not. The results revealed diverse opinions among the participants (Table 3). The values in parentheses are percentages representing the proportion of students agreeing, disagreeing, or undecided on each attitude. Values outside parentheses indicate the actual number of students corresponding to the percentage.

Table 3: Student attitude towards biology practical.

Items	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
Biology practical inspires me to read ahead of the teacher	154(64)	58(24)	29(12)
Biology practical encourages me to excel in Biology	46(19)	175(73)	19(8)
Biology practical makes me work hard towards attaining quality grades	36(15)	166(69)	38(16)
Biology practical challenges me to improve my performance in the biology subject	65(27)	156(65)	19(8)
I feel anxious and fearful during the biology practical examination	118(49)	108(45)	14(6)
I have adequate learning resources	96(40)	127(53)	17(7)
Biology practical work is technical to learn	125(52)	108(45)	7(3)

The students in three different school categories (mixed schools, boys' schools, and girls' schools) were given a biology practical test during the study and the data were collected on how they performed. The overall mean scores of the Biology Practical Assessment Test (BPAT) (X/20) for the school types are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Students' mean performance in biology practical assessment test per school category (The assessment was marked out of 20).

School Category	No. students	Max	Min	Mean
Female school	60	15	2	9.66±0.8
Male school	61	17	3	7.82±1.6
Mixed school	119	18	4	6.47±1.3
Test for statistical significance				
F value	-	-	-	3.32
P value	-	-	-	0.03

The findings provide valuable insights into the students' academic achievements under different categories. There was significant variation in performance among the school categories (F=3.32, P=0.03), with girls' schools displaying the highest mean score of 9.66±0.8, suggesting better performance compared to Boys' schools (mean score of 7.82±1.6) and Mixed schools (mean score of 6.47±1.3). The present study presents contradicting results to the findings of Eddy *et al.* (2014), which indicated that females consistently underperform in practical biology examinations when compared to their male counterparts.

Effective teaching strategies and a supportive learning environment specific to girls' needs may have contributed to their success. In contrast, Boys' schools' lower performance could be attributed to various factors, such as inadequate resources or challenges affecting boys' engagement and motivation. The mixed nature of mixed schools, with diverse student

backgrounds, may account for the variation in mean scores (Amedu, 2015). The statistically significant results from the ANOVA test ($F_{2, 235} = 3.32$, $P = 0.03$) highlight significant differences among school categories. Policymakers and educators can use these findings to implement targeted interventions and strategies to enhance academic performance and foster an inclusive learning environment.

Students' attitudes towards Biology practical and science, in general, are influenced by various factors, including prior experiences, perceptions of usefulness and difficulty, and the type of school they attend. For instance, single-sex schools may create a more comfortable environment for students to participate in Biology practicals without gender stereotypes, potentially enhancing their engagement. On the other hand, mixed schools may subject students to pressure to conform to gender norms, affecting their willingness to participate in certain biology practical activities (DFID, 2007). Addressing these variations in attitudes across different school categories can significantly contribute to overall academic achievement and promote holistic development in the field of biology and beyond.

5. CONCLUSION

The study found a link between school categories and students' attitudes towards biology practical work, as well as their subsequent performance. In comparison to boys' and mixed schools, female schools stood out as inspiring and encouraging environments, with higher percentages of students feeling motivated and excelling in biology through practical tests. Furthermore, private school students were more enthusiastic about improving their performance and perceived more challenges, resulting in higher test scores than their public-school counterparts. Further, school categories based on administration and academic characteristics influenced the students' performance, with Extra-County schools displaying superior mean performance in the biology practical test compared to County and Sub-County schools. These findings emphasize the crucial role of school characteristics in shaping students' attitudes and achievements in Biology practical work, providing valuable insights for educational strategies and interventions.

6. RECOMMENDATION

Given the significant association between school categories and students' attitudes and achievements in biology practical work, educators should tailor teaching strategies based on school characteristics. Schools should identify their unique strengths and weaknesses in biology education and implement targeted interventions to enhance student engagement and success. For instance, boys' schools and mixed schools could learn from the positive outcomes observed in girls' schools and adopt similar practices that foster inspiration and motivation in practical learning.

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